

Tutorial Series on Java Framework for Evolutionary Computation and Decision Making

Tutorial 14: Introducing builders dedicated to the pre-configured algorithms

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Abstract

This tutorial showcases new builder classes that assist in instantiating the framework's pre-configured algorithms.

Keywords: JECDM, EA, evolutionary algorithm, builders

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1. Introduction

So far, concrete implementations of the algorithms could be obtained via factory-like static methods, e.g., `NSGAII.getNSGAII(...)`. Nonetheless, due to the high configurability of these implementations, the available static methods became somewhat cumbersome and not readable over time. To alleviate these problems, dedicated builder classes have been introduced since v.1.8.0 of the framework, e.g.:

- `NSGA` → `NSGABuilder` class,
- `NSGAII` → `NSGAIIBuilder` class,
- `NSGAIII` → `NSGAIIIBuilder` class,

and so on. They offer the possibility to represent the configuration as a step-by-step pre-building process, while also providing various auxiliary adjustment and validation procedures. In this tutorial, two example use cases are presented: configuring the NSGA-II [1] and IEMO/D [2] algorithms.

2. Instantiating NSGA-II [T]

Source package:
`t11_t20.t14_using_builders.Tutorial1`

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This tutorial demonstrates how to use a dedicated `NSGAIIBuilder` class to instantiate the NSGAII algorithm. The construction process is relatively straightforward and is presented in Listings 1-4.

First, Listing 1 begins by instantiating the builder already coupled with a random number generator. The latter is assumed to be a final field; thus, it must be provided now. The example assumes that the NSGA-II will be run to solve a simple 2-dimensional DTLZ2 problem. To facilitate the configuration process, the code instantiates a dedicated `DTLZBundle` object that provides various problem-specific data. Next, the builder is used to set the criteria (obtained from the problem bundle), population size, and parent selection procedure (a tournament of size 2).

Listing 1: Instantiating NSGA-II (p. 1)

```
// First, instantiate the relevant builder
// object (the random number generator is
// final and must be provided
// via the constructor):
NSGAIIBuilder b = new NSGAIIBuilder(new
    L32_X64_MIX(0));

// We will parameterize the method to solve
// a simple DTLZ2 problem with 2 objective
// functions.
// For this purpose, we can create a bundle
// , which will facilitate the NSGA-
// construction process:
DTLZBundle dtlzBundle = DTLZBundle.
    getBundle(
        Problem.DTLZ2, 2, 10); //
        params: problem,
        objectives, distance-
        related parameters

b.setCriteria(dtlzBundle._criteria); // set
criteria definitions
```

```

b.setPopulationSize(100); // set population
    size
b.setParentsSelector(new Tournament(2)); //
    use tournament selection
}

```

Side note on selection: The algorithms that explicitly rely on sorting solutions are designed in JECDM so that they additionally set the specimens' auxiliary score values. These values are consistent, i.e., their ordering, with the order imposed on the specimens by the algorithm (the scoring pattern is included in the method's Java docs). Various selection procedures can then compare specimens by using these auxiliary scores when selecting parents, instead of performing some additional – and redundant – calculations. It is the case of the default object instance of the *Tournament* class. Nonetheless, the *Tournament* object can now be instantiated with an implementation of an auxiliary *IComparator* interface to customize the specimen comparison process (i.e., to determine the tournament winner). An example is presented in Listing 2.

Listing 2: Instantiating NSGA-II (p. 2)

```

// IMPORTANT note: the implementation of
// the tournament selection assumes
// comparing specimens by their first
// auxiliary score values; the implemented
// sorting procedure of NSGA-II sets these
// values in a way that the
// non-dominated + crowding distance
// indications are preserved (lower values
// are preferred; (see the extract from
// the builder's java doc). Nonetheless,
// one can customize the comparison rule in
// the tournament selection to
5 // serve various needs in the following way
// :
b.setParentsSelector(new Tournament(2, new
    IComparator()
{
    /**
    * The main method for comparing two
    * specimens.
10 *
    * @param A the first specimen
    * @param B the second specimen
    * @return 1 if A is considered better,
    *         -1 if B is considered better, 0 in
    *         the case of a draw.
    */
15 *//
@Override
public int compare(Specimen A, Specimen B
    )
{
    // NOTE that the below is the default
    // comparator used by the Tournament
    // class (one does not need to
    // specify it).
20 return Double.compare(A.getAlternative
    ().getAuxScore(), B.getAlternative()
    .getAuxScore());
}
}

```

```

})));
}

```

Next, Listing 3 parameterizes the builder with a procedure for creating an initial population, evaluating specimens, and reproducing the selected parents. As for the reproducer, two example uses are presented for convenience. First, a default reproduced provided by the problem bundle is set. Second, which overwrites the first, a custom *StandardDoubleReproducer* is defined with specified crossover (*SBX*), mutation (*PM*, optional), and variable values validation (reflection around the bounds of [0, 1]; optional) procedures. Lastly, Listing 3 tunes the method to dynamically learn about true Pareto front bounds, which are in turn used to define suitable normalization functions used by NSGA-II when calculating crowding distances.

Listing 3: Instantiating NSGA-II (p. 3)

```

b.setInitialPopulationConstructor(
    dtlzBundle._construct); // set the
// initial population constructor
b.setSpecimensEvaluator(dtlzBundle.
    _evaluate); // set specimens evaluator
b.setParentsReproducer(dtlzBundle.
    _reproduce); // set the default
// reproducer that is provided by the
// bundle...
// or define own processing (assumption:
// the solutions use double representations
// and one offspring is always
// constructed from two parents):
b.setParentsReproducer(new
    StandardDoubleReproducer( // overwrites
// the previous setter
    new SBX(1.0d, 20.0d), // SBX crossover
    new PM(1.0d / (10.0d + 1.0d), 20.0d), //
    PM mutation
    // parameters specifying the decision-
    // variable bounds and a variable
    // repairing procedure:
10 new Reflect(), 0.0d, 1.0d
));
b.setDynamicOSBoundsLearningPolicy(); //
// NSGA-II will initially know nothing
// about the Pareto front bounds and
// is set to learn them dynamically during
// evolution
15 }

```

Lastly, Listing 4 derives the instance of the NSGA-II algorithm and runs it for 500 generations. Note that the process is within the *try-catch* block. The builder's *getInstance()* method performs simple (shallow) validation and will throw an exception if some necessary components are not set. For instance, if one comments the *b.setInitialPopulationConstructor(dtlzBundle._construct);* line, an error with a message “*The initial population constructor is not provided*” will be thrown.

Listing 4: Instantiating NSGA-II (p. 4)

```

try
{
    // Instantiating the method can be done
    // in the following way. The method will
    // throw a checked exception
    // if some parameterization means are
    // missing:
5   NSGAI nsgai = b.getInstance();
    Runner runner = new Runner(nsgai);
    runner.executeEvolution(500);
    // Print population:
    for (Specimen s : nsgai.
        getSpecimensContainer().getPopulation
        ())
10    PrintUtils.printVectorOfDoubles(s.
        getPerformanceVector(), 5);
} catch (EAException | RunnerException e)
{
    System.out.println(e.getMessage());
}
15 }

```

3. Instantiating IEMO/D [T]

Source package:
t11_t20.t14_using_builders.Tutorial2

This tutorial demonstrates how to instantiate an interactive preference-learning IEMO/D algorithm. As with the previous example, IEMO/D is tuned to solve a standard 2-dimensional DTLZ2 problem and follows a similar parameterization that is presented in Listing 5. Some differences refer to the implementation-specific requirements. As a decomposition-based method founded on the MOEA/D framework [3], IEMO/D must be coupled with a series of scalarizing goals used to steer the evolution (*b.setGoals(...)*). Also, a measure quantifying similarity between goals and the neighborhood size must be specified. Lastly, observe that the method is tuned not to learn the Pareto front bounds dynamically. Instead, the required data is provided a priori and assumed fixed (*b.setFixedOSBoundsLearningPolicy*). Note that an assumption on the dynamic learning of these bounds imposes greater algorithmic design challenges in preference learning methods. These are discussed in the 16-th tutorial document.

Listing 5: Instantiating IEMO/D (p. 1)

```

// First, instantiate the relevant builder
// object (the random number generator is
// final and must be provided
// via the constructor):
IEMODBuilder<LNorm> b = new IEMODBuilder<>(
    new L32_X64_MIX(0));
5
// We will parameterize the method to solve
// a simple DTLZ2 problem with 2 objective
// functions.

```

```

// For this purpose, we can create a bundle
// , which will facilitate the IEMOD-
// construction process:
DTLZBundle dtlzBundle = DTLZBundle.
    getBundle(
        Problem.DTLZ2, 2, 10); //
        params: problem,
        objectives, distance-
        related parameters
10 b.setCriteria(dtlzBundle._criteria); // set
    criteria definitions
// Set the optimization goals for IEMO/D:
b.setGoals(GoalsFactory.getLNormsDND(2, 99,
    Double.POSITIVE_INFINITY, dtlzBundle.
    _normalizations));
int ps = b.getGoals().length; // derive the
    population size for the following
    parameterization
b.setSimilarity(new emo.utils.decomposition
    .similarity.lnorm.Euclidean()); //
    define the similarity measure
// between the goals
b.setNeighborhoodSize(10); // set the
    neighborhood size
b.setParentsSelector(new Random()); // set
    the random selection of parents (IEMO/D
    is founded on MOEA/D that
    // uses a restricted mating pool)
20 b.setInitialPopulationConstructor(
    dtlzBundle._construct); // set the
    initial population constructor
b.setSpecimensEvaluator(dtlzBundle.
    _evaluate); // set specimens evaluator
b.setParentsReproducer(new
    StandardDoubleReproducer( // define the
    reproducer:
    new SBX(1.0d, 20.0d), // SBX crossover
    new PM(1.0d / (10.0d + 1.0d), 20.0d), //
    PM mutation
    // parameters specifying the decision-
    // variable bounds and a variable
    // repairing procedure:
    new Reflect(), 0.0d, 1.0d
    ));
// We will assume that the algorithm knows
// the Pareto front bounds from the
// beginning:
30 b.setFixedOSBoundsLearningPolicy(dtlzBundle
    ._normalizations, dtlzBundle._utopia,
    dtlzBundle._nadir);
// Note that the dynamic adjustment of the
// known Pareto front bounds is a
// relatively complex concept
// in preference-learning methods. It is
// somewhat covered in tutorial 15.
}

```

Next, Listing 6 concerns the configuration that is related to

preference-learning. It involves instantiating and suitably parameterizing a decision support system builder (*StandardDSSBuilder*). This builder assumes a standard configuration with one decision-maker, one decision-maker's assumed preference model, one preference learning method, and one reference set construction policy. Specifically, the configuration is as follows:

1. The decision-maker's preferences are assumed to be modeled with L-norms (*bD.setPreferenceModel(...)*).
2. The true decision-maker is assumed to be questioned every 20 generations, starting from 200-th generation, with the imposed limit of 10 interactions in total (*bD.setInteractionRule(...)*).
3. During the interaction, two random solutions are to be picked for a critical evaluation by the decision-maker (*bD.setReferenceSetConstructor(...)*).
4. It is assumed that the decision-maker's responses (pair-wise comparisons) are to be simulated using an artificial decision-maker whose value system is modeled with a weighted Chebyshev function with equal weights (*bD.setDMFeedbackProvider(...)*).
5. As for the preference learning procedure, an Evolutionary Rejection Sampling algorithm with the limit of 100000 evolutionary steps is used (*bD.setModelConstructor(...)*).

Listing 6: Instantiating IEMO/D (p. 2)

```
// The preference-based IEMO/D requires the
// instantiation of a decision-support
// system. It is done via
// a suitably parameterized builder:
StandardDSSBuilder<LNorm> bD = new
StandardDSSBuilder<>();
bD.setPreferenceModel(new model.definitions
.LNorm()); // define the assumed
// preference model (L-norm)
bD.setInteractionRule(new IterationInterval
(200, 20, 10)); // define the
// interaction
// rule (starting from 200th generation,
// after every 20 generations, assume the
// limit of 10 interactions)
bD.setReferenceSetConstructor(new
RandomPairs(new RequiredSpread(1.0E-6)))
; // use a reference set
// constructor that prepares a random pair
// of solutions to be compared by the DM
// Use the model of an artificial DM to
// compare the solutions. This example
// assumes that it is modelled using
// a weighted Chebyshev function with
// equal weights:
bD.setDMFeedbackProvider(new
ArtificialValueDM<>(new model.
definitions.LNorm(
```

```
new LNorm(new double []{0.5d
, 0.5d}, Double.
POSITIVE_INFINITY,
dtlzBundle.
_normalizations)))));
// This example uses the Evolutionary
// Rejection Sampling method as the
// preference-learning procedure:
ERS.Params<LNorm> pERS = new ERS.Params<>(
new LNormGenerator(2,
Double.POSITIVE_INFINITY
, dtlzBundle.
_normalizations));
pERS._similarity = new Euclidean();
pERS._feasibleSamplesToGenerate = ps;
pERS._inconsistencyThreshold = ps - 1;
pERS._iterationsLimit = new Constant
(100000);
pERS._EMC = new
EvolutionaryModelConstructor<>(
new LNormOnSimplex(Double.
POSITIVE_INFINITY, 0.2d,
0.2d),
new Tournament<>(2));
bD.setModelConstructor(new ERS<>(pERS));
b.setStandardDSSBuilder(bD);
}
```

Finally, Listing 7 demonstrates how to instantiate the algorithm and run it for 500 generations. Since the decision-maker's preferences are modeled using a Chebyshev function with weights = [0.5, 0.5] and the problem is DTLZ2, it is expected that the method will suitably learn the true decision-maker's aspiration and accordingly narrow the search around the 'middle' Pareto optimal solution, which is $\approx [0.71, 0.71]$. The algorithm was indeed capable of performing such convergence, which can be confirmed by the performance vectors associated with the final population members, printed at the end to the console (see Figure 1).

Listing 7: Instantiating IEMO/D (p. 3)

```
try
{
// Instantiating the method can be done
// in the following way. The method will
// throw a checked exception
// if some parameterization means are
// missing:
IEMOD iemod = b.getInstance();
Runner runner = new Runner(iemod, ps);
// IMPORTANT NOTE: since IEMO/D is a
// preference-learning method, a more
// demanding approach than the regular
// NSGA-II algorithm, the optimization
// process may take more time:
runner.executeEvolution(500);
// Print population. NOTE that the final
// specimens are expected to be located
// around the Pareto front's
// middle solution, i.e., around the
```

```

    [0.7, 0.7] coordinate.
for (Specimen s : iemod.
    getSpecimensContainer().getPopulation
    ())
    PrintUtils.printVectorOfDoubles(s.
        getPerformanceVector(), 5);
} catch (EAException | RunnerException e)
{
    System.out.println(e.getMessage());
}

```

```

0,70831 0,70571
0,70849 0,70572
0,70722 0,70699
0,70724 0,70698
0,70886 0,70536
0,70891 0,70530
0,70727 0,70694
0,70728 0,70694
0,70831 0,70591
0,70888 0,70534
0,70889 0,70532
0,70762 0,70660
0,70767 0,70655
0,70836 0,70586
0,70764 0,70658
0,70765 0,70657
0,70833 0,70589
0,70834 0,70587

Process finished with exit code 0

```

Figure 1: Console output

References

- [1] Deb, K., Pratap, A., Agarwal, S., Meyarivan, T., 2000. A fast and elitist multiobjective genetic algorithm: NSGA-II. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation* 6, 182–197. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/4235.996017>.
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- [3] Zhang, Q., Li, H., 2007. MOEA/D: A multiobjective evolutionary algorithm based on decomposition. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation* 11, 712–731. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEVC.2007.892759>.